

Molecular Size of Cellulose from Different Sources. Part I.

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The problem of the identity of different celluloses was investigated in a *qualitative* manner by Chowdhury and Bose (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 615) who concluded that they were all made up entirely of anhydroglucose units though the number of these units differed in different cases. One of the objects of the present investigations was to determine *quantitatively* the actual number of anhydroglucose units in different celluloses.

As is well known, Staudinger, from a careful study of viscosity measurements, found a relationship between viscosity and molecular weight of polymer homologues as expressed by

$$\eta_{sp}/C = k_m \cdot M \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

Where η_{sp} denotes specific viscosity, c , primary molar concentration, K_m , a constant for each polymer homologous series and M , the molecular weight. This formula has been verified in the case of hydrocarbons as well as synthetic polymers upto the molecular weight of about 10,000. It has been found that the molecular weights determined by this method as well as by the chemical and cryoscopic methods agree in a remarkable manner. By applying the K_m constant, determined from comparatively low molecular polymer homologues and checked by molecular weight determination by other methods, Staudinger obtained molecular weights as high as 200,000, a figure which cannot be even dreamt of by the application of other methods at our disposal

Though the formula is empirical in nature, Staudinger made an attempt to derive it, on certain assumptions, from the Einstein formula in the following manner :

$$\eta_r = \eta_o \left(1 + K_1 \frac{N \cdot Q}{V} \right) \quad (ii)$$

where η_r denotes viscosity of the solution, η_o , the viscosity of solvent,

V , the total volume of solution, N , the number of solute molecules each of which has a volume Q , and K_1 , a constant. Hence

$$\eta_c/\eta_o = \eta_r = 1 + K_1 \frac{NQ}{V}$$

$$\text{or} \quad \eta_r - 1 = \eta_{s,p} = K_1 \frac{NQ}{V}$$

where η_r is the relative viscosity and $\eta_{s,p}$, the specific viscosity.

As $NM/V = C$ and $k = K_2M$, in the case of polymer homologues the equation may be given the following form :

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_{s,p}/C &= K_1 \frac{NQ}{V} \cdot \frac{V}{NM} = \frac{K_1 Q}{M} = \frac{K_1 \cdot \pi \tau^2 h}{M} \\ &= \frac{K_1 \pi \tau^2 K_2 M}{M} = K \end{aligned}$$

where τ denotes the radius and h , the length of the molecule.

Thus if Einstein formula were applicable to long fibre molecules, the specific viscosity should vary proportionately with concentration and would be independent of the number of molecules of the dispersed phase in polymer homologues so long as the diameter of the molecules remained the same, *i.e.*, the specific viscosity would not be affected if dissolved phase were divided into many small divisions or consisted of a few large molecules of the same diameter. This, however, is not found true by actual measurements of viscosity in the case of long fibre molecules which are found to have an altogether different relationship expressed by the empirical formula (i) of Staudinger.

Staudinger attempts to explain this inapplicability of Einstein formula in the case of fibre molecules by assuming that the total volume of the dissolved phase in the case of fibre molecules is not identical with the actual volume of these long molecules which, by their vibration, hinder the free motion of a part of the solvent and hence increase the viscosity abnormally. The total "effective volume" is, therefore, equal to the sum of the volume of the molecules and the volume of the immobilised solvent molecules.

This effective volume has been calculated by Staudinger by supposing the long fibre molecules to vibrate in such a manner that the total volume of its activity is equal to that of a flat cylinder having the

diameter of the molecule as its height and the length as its diameter, so that the effective volume

$$Q_1 = \pi \left(\frac{h}{2} \right)^2 \cdot 2r.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Hence } \eta_{sp}/C &= \frac{K_1 Q_1}{M} = \frac{K_1}{M} \cdot \pi \left(\frac{h}{2} \right)^2 \cdot 2r = \frac{K_1}{M} \cdot \left(\frac{K_2 M}{2} \right)^2 \cdot \pi \cdot 2r \\ &= \left(K_1 K_2^2 \pi \frac{2r}{4} \right) \cdot M = K_m \cdot M. \end{aligned}$$

This assumption of the effective volume appears rather arbitrary. It cannot be understood why the effective volume should be like that of a flat cylinder instead of a sphere, as the large molecules are free to vibrate in all possible directions, specially in dilute solutions. The Staudinger formula must, therefore, be taken as entirely empirical and should not be applied without proper investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Standard Cellulose.—It is of essential importance that the different celluloses investigated should be as pure as possible and should be subjected to the same treatment if comparative results are aimed at.

The alcohol-benzol extracted cotton, delignified jute or bamboo was first extracted with a large volume of 1% caustic soda and then with boiling water (3 times). This was followed by alternate treatment with 17.5% caustic soda solution in the cold and 5% boiling caustic soda solution (5 times) with careful exclusion of air. The sample was then washed free from alkali and dried in air.

The analytical data of the different celluloses thus purified is given below.

TABLE I.

	Cotton.	Jute.	Bamboo.
Lignin	Nil	Nil	Nil
Furfural	1.17%	1.12%	1.2%
Fats and resins	Nil	Nil	Nil
Ash	0.05	0.23	0.52
Moisture	8.2	10.1	11.5
Uronic acid	Nil	Nil	Nil
Solubility			
in 17.5% alkali	1.95	1.92	2.2

Preparation of Schweitzer's Reagent.—The preparation of this solvent with a constant composition was effected by the method of Joyner (*Cellulose Chem.*, 1930, 11, 105) slightly modified to suit new conditions. A glass jar (45 cm. $\times$ 10 cm.) was filled with clean copper turnings and then with liquor ammonia (29%) containing 1% cane sugar and was surrounded by a cold bath of ice. The jar was fitted with a reflux condenser and a mild stream of cooled air was continually passed through the solution for 24 to 26 hours. The solvent thus prepared was kept in a dark bottle in a cool place. The composition of the solvent was $\text{Cu} = 30 \pm 2$ g./ litre and $\text{NH}_3 = 165 \pm 2$ g./ litre.

FIG. 1.

G—Glass filter. S—Dissolving tube.

The arrangement described by the Cellulose Division of the American Chemical Society (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, Anal. Ed., 1929, 1, 50) was generally followed in order to effect the solution of cellulose in absence of air in Schweitzer's reagent. This solution was passed through a glass filter before leading it into the Ostwald tube.

Viscosity Measurements in an Inert Atmosphere.—The actual measurement of viscosity was carried out by means of an Ostwald tube (Fig. 1). A current of dry hydrogen was passed through the apparatus for about 30 minutes to ensure complete removal of air and by careful manipulation, a definite volume of the solution in the dissolving tube S was introduced into the Ostwald tube through the glass filter to remove traces of any mechanical impurity. The temperature of the thermostat was regulated up to $\pm 0.05^\circ$. The densities of the solutions were measured by means of a sp. gr. bottle.

Viscosity and Concentration.—It has already been mentioned that before applying the Staudinger formula for the determination of molecular weight, it is necessary to investigate the limit of concentration in which any relationship between viscosity and concentration can be established. According to the Einstein formula, viscosity should vary proportionately with concentration. It will be noticed from curve in Fig. 2 that this is true only in very dilute solution when the concentration is below 0.075% and viscosity below 1.9. As the concentration increases, the curve bends upwards showing that viscosity increases to a greater extent. This inapplicability of Einstein formula in the case of substances of high molecular weight has also been observed by other workers who attempted to put forward new formulæ showing relationship of viscosity and concentration but they were all empirical in nature and were applicable only within short ranges of concentration.

FIG. 2.
Cotton cellulose at 28°.

FIG. 3.

The steep rise of viscosity with higher concentration may be due to the action of one molecule on another, which increases the inner friction of the solution or to the volume of the solute being appreciable in comparison with the volume of the solvent. Following the same principles as those of Van der Waals in his modification of the gas laws, Mark and Fikentscher have tried to express this steep rise by the following modification of the Einstein formula

$$\eta_r = 1 + \frac{K_1 N Q}{V - N Q}$$

This modification, no doubt, explains the steep rise of viscosity with increase in the number of solute particles and hence with concentration. But this equation also fails to agree with actual facts if the concentration is varied within a wide range. Evidently it is only in very dilute solutions that any relationship between viscosity and concentration may be expected to hold. This is further reflected in the figures of molecular weights of cotton, jute, and bamboo celluloses which remain constant only when based on viscosity measurements at very low concentrations.

Molecular Weights of Different Celluloses.

The viscosity measurements were carried out at 28° and at 34° and the molecular weights were calculated with the help of the Staudinger

formula, taking the value of K_m as 10×10^{-4} , the calculations being based on ash and moisture free cellulose.

It will be observed that the figures for molecular weights of cotton, jute and bamboo celluloses rise abruptly above the concentration of 0.042%, 0.058% and 0.122% respectively. As the change of temperature does not affect these figures, solvation or micelle formation does not seem to be the cause of such abnormal behaviour. The passing of the 'sol' solution to 'gel' solution as suggested by Staudinger or the influence of one molecule on the free vibration of another may possibly be responsible for such irregularity. It will be observed from Tables II-IV, that the molecular weight of cotton cellulose is 158200, that of jute cellulose 83680 and that of bamboo cellulose is 30590 approximately. The number of anhydroglucose units in these celluloses are, therefore, 978, 516 and 189 respectively.

FIG. 4.

Cellulose at 28°.

Fig. 5.

Viscose in NaOH soln. at 35°.

FIG. 6.

Cellulose triacetate in m-cresole at 24°.

TABLE II.

Viscosity of cotton cellulose in Schweitzer's reagent.

Composition of the solvent = Cu, 28.5 g./litre ; NH₃, 161.2 g./litre.

Conc.	Primary mol. conc.	Temp = 28°.		Temp = 34°.	
		$\eta_{sp.}$	M.W.	$\eta_{sp.}$	M. W.
0.009175%	0.0005663	0.09	159000	0.09	159000
0.01835	0.001133	0.173	158000	0.178	157000
0.02752	0.001698	0.268	157800	0.267	157200
0.04129	0.002549	0.403	158100	0.403	158100
0.05321	0.003285	0.608	185100	0.611	186000
0.06422	0.003964	0.774	195300	0.770	194300
0.09175	0.005663	1.209	213700	1.209	213500
0.1376	0.008494	2.218	261100	2.211	260300
0.1835	0.01133	3.399	300000	3.465	385800
0.2569	0.0186	5.735	361600	5.722	360800

TABLE III.

Viscosity of jute cellulose in Schweitzer's reagent.

Composition of the solvent—same as in Table II.

Conc.	Primary mol. conc.	Temp = 28°.		Temp = 34°.	
		η_{sp} .	M. W.	η_{sp}	M. W.
0'008967%	0'0005535	0'046	83120	0'045	84150
0'01794	0'001108	0'093	83950	0'093	83620
0'03588	0'002215	0'187	84410	0'188	84870
0'0583	0'003599	0'298	83260	0'302	83910
0'07176	0'004430	0'407	91870	0'410	92550
0'08967	0'005535	0'531	95940	0'529	96380
0'1346	0'008310	0'834	100300	0'834	100200
0'1794	0'01108	1'291	116500	1'284	115700
0'2512	0'01551	2'020	130200	2'016	130000

TABLE IV.

*Viscosity of bamboo cellulose in Schweitzer's reagent.*Composition of the solvent = Cu, 30'2 g./litre; NH₃, 166 g./litre.

Conc.	Primary Mol. conc.	Temp = 28°.		Temp = 35°.	
		η_{sp} .	M. W.	η_{sp}	M. W.
0'03250%	0'002173	0'067	31550	0'064	29450
0'06259	0'003802	0'1177	30770	0'117	30770
0'08798	0'005431	0'169	31120	0'165	30380
0'1215	0'007501	0'229	30520	0'2284	30450
0'1884	0'009779	0'328	33320	0'3287	33620
0'2112	0'01304	0'474	36360	0'4755	36500
0'2462	0'01520	0'600	39490	0'6034	39700

Molecular Weight of Cellulose in Viscose Solution.

In view of the industrial importance of viscose, the molecular weight of different celluloses in this solution was also investigated with the result that a somewhat lower value was obtained in this case though the same materials were used. Evidently, during the preparation of viscose, cellulose is to some extent disintegrated, the number of anhydroglucose units in cotton, jute and bamboo celluloses being 894, 468 and 158 respectively. Another interesting point is that the molecular weight remains constant to a somewhat higher range of concentration, *i.e.*, 0.054%, 0.072%, 0.185% respectively. This rise in limiting viscosity is in agreement with the partial degradation of the cellulose molecule.

A known weight of cellulose was dipped in CS₂ for 1 hour, the excess poured off and 20 c.c. of 16.91% NaOH solution were added and shaken for one hour. It was then made up to 100 c.c. with 4.94% NaOH, 10 c. c. being added every half an hour. The solution was then diluted to 500 c. c. and filtered. Preparation of viscose and measurement of viscosity were completed in about the same time in all cases. Results are shown in Table V.

TABLE V.
Molecular weight of different celluloses in viscose.

Temp = 35°.

Material.	Conc.	Primary mol conc	η_{sp} .	M W.
Cotton	0.009175%	0.0005663	0.082	144800
	0.02752	0.001698	0.247	145400
	0.04129	0.002549	0.37	145200
	0.05321	0.003285	0.473	144100
	0.06122	0.003924	0.603	153400
	0.09175	0.005663	0.899	158800
Jute	0.006967	0.0005535	0.042	75880
	0.03588	0.002215	0.169	76300
	0.0583	0.003599	0.270	75020
	0.07176	0.004430	0.339	76520
	0.08967	0.005335	0.439	79320
	0.1316	0.008310	0.693	83390
Bamboo	0.03520	0.002173	0.055	25310
	0.0615	0.003802	0.098	25770
	0.1215	0.007501	0.170	26150
	0.1848	0.01111	0.287	25160
	0.2112	0.01304	0.363	27840
	0.2462	0.01520	0.445	29280

Molecular Weight of Cellulose Triacetate in m-Cresol

Determination of molecular weight in the case of cellulose acetate shows a further degradation during acetylation, though special care was taken to follow a method which would minimise degradation. As the acetate thus prepared was not completely soluble in ordinary solvents, *m*-cresol was used for the purpose and special care was taken to avoid absorption of water vapour by the solvent. The molecular weights of cotton acetate and jute acetate are found to be 39870, 24920 respectively, which give the number of anhydroglucose units in the case of cotton and jute as 138 and 86 respectively. In this case, the limiting concentration is still higher, being 0.16%, and 0.18% respectively in the case of cotton and jute acetates.

In acetylation, it was necessary to adopt a method which would not seriously affect the cellulose. For this purpose Barnett's method as modified in this laboratory (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **9**, 618) was followed. The acetyl contents of the products were 43.85%, 43.2% in the case of cotton and jute respectively. The solution of the acetates were effected in distilled *m*-cresol. Measurements of viscosity was made after the solution had stood for sometime in the Ostwald tube.

TABLE VI.

Viscosity of cotton triacetate in m-cresol.

Conc.	Primary mol. conc.	Temp. = 28°.		Temp. = 34°.	
		$\eta_{sp.}$	M. W.	$\eta_{sp.}$	M. W.
0.035%	0.001215	0.053	39660	0.053	39660
0.067	0.002327	0.101	39460	0.103	40240
0.1082	0.003757	0.167	40410	0.166	40170
0.1604	0.005569	0.244	39950	0.245	39990
0.2008	0.006971	0.320	42900	0.330	43030
0.2412	0.008375	0.416	45150	0.418	45370
0.3476	0.01207	0.696	52420	0.700	52720

TABLE VII.

Viscosity of jute triacetate in m-cresol.

Conc.	Primary mol. conc.	Temp. = 28°.		Temp = 34°.	
		$\eta_{sp.}$	M. W.	$\eta_{sp.}$	M. W.
0.0315%	0.001099	0.0301	25100	0.0303	25200
0.0616	0.002139	0.058	24650	0.058	24650
0.123	0.004271	0.121	25870	0.120	25550
0.1638	0.005689	0.155	24770	0.152	24300
0.1812	0.006292	0.178	25710	0.174	25170
0.2134	0.007409	0.219	26870	0.220	27000
0.3421	0.01184	0.468	35920	0.467	33460

Molecular Weight of Degraded Cellulose.

If cellulose is treated with 42% HCl, at 0°, it is found that a white amorphous product, insoluble in water and in other ordinary solvents but soluble in Schweitzer's reagent, is obtained. The molecular weight of this product in Schweitzer's reagent (Table VIII) shows that cellulose molecules have been considerably disintegrated during the formation of this so-called cello-dextrin. The cello-dextrins from cotton and jute have molecular weights of 2088, and 1479 respectively and hence the number of anhydroglucose units are 13, and 9 respectively. This low number of anhydroglucose molecules explains the absence of fibre-structure in the degraded product.

10 G. of finely shredded cellulose were placed in a stoppered bottle and cooled in a refrigerator for about 1 hour. About 350 c.c. of cooled 42% HCl were then added and the bottle kept in the refrigerator for 7-8 hours with occasional shaking. At the end of this period all the cellulose had gone into solution which was then poured into about 2½ litres of cooled distilled water, when the product slowly separated and was allowed to stand overnight, washed free from acid and dried. As the product was very much degraded, comparatively stronger solutions were used for viscosity measurements.

TABLE VIII.

*Viscosity of degradation product in Schweitzer's reagent.*Cu = 28.8 g./litre; NH₃ = 165.4 g./litre. Temp. = 35°.

Material.	Conc. cotton.	Primary mol. conc.	$\eta_{sp.}$	M. W.
Cotton	1.9172%	0.09365	0.190	2124
	2.4213	0.1495	0.313	2093
	3.3065	0.2041	0.420	2058
Jute	1.3544	0.08373	0.1265	1510
	2.0186	0.1246	0.180	1445
	3.4215	0.2112	0.313	1482

CONCLUSION.

It is evident that the celluloses from different sources are not identical and that their different physical properties are inherent in the size of the molecule and are not due to differences in physical conditions only. In Schweitzer's reagent, cotton, jute and bamboo are found to be composed of 978, 516 and 189 anhydroglucose units. In viscose, the cellulose is somewhat disintegrated, the cotton, jute and bamboo celluloses consisting of 894, 468 and 158 units of anhydroglucose. In acetylation, the disintegration proceeds further and the molecules are found to consist of 138, 86 residues of glucose in the cases of cotton and jute respectively. The disintegration can be carried still further by treatment with 42% HCl at 0°, when the molecules are found to consist of 13 and 9 glucose units only in the case of cotton and jute. The number of glucose units in native cotton cellulose is still higher and may be estimated as over 1000 anhydroglucose molecules, if the K_m constant, as experimentally determined by Staudinger in case of lower homologues, be applicable to the higher homologues as well.